

Deliverable D8.7 – Update of the Data Management Plan

WP8 – Update of the Data Management Plan

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
API	Application Program Interface
AR6	Sixth Assessment Report of the IPCC
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, a license
CCI	Common Cloud Infrastructure
CDS	Copernicus Climate Data Store
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Service
CF	Climate and Forecasting
CHELSA	Climatologies at high resolution for the Earth's land surface areas
CLIMAAX	Climate risk and vulnerability assessment framework and toolbox
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CMCC	Euro-Mediterranean Centre on Climate Change
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CoP	Community of Practice
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment
CORINE	Copernicus Land Cover (CLC) inventory
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DMP	Data Management plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ECLIPS	European Climate Index Projections
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasting
EFFIS	European Forest Fire Information System
ERA5	Global atmospheric reanalysis from ECMWF (fifth version)
EROS	Earth Resources Observation and Science
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FGGD	Food Insecurity, Poverty and Environment Global GIS Database
FSTP	Financial support to third parties
FWI	Fire Weather Index
GAEZ	Global Agro-Ecological Zones
GeoJSON	Geographical JavaScript Object Notation
GeoTIFF	Georeferenced Tag Image File Format
GHSL	Global Human Settlement Layer
GIS	Geographic Information System
GISCO	Geographic Information System of the (European) Commission
GRIB	General Regularly distributed Information in Binary form
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IDF	Intensity, Duration, Frequency
IFPRI	International Food Policy Research Institute
IIASA	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISIMIP	Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Group, short for an image file format
JRC	Joint Research Centre of the European Commission
LUISA	Land Use Integrated Sustainability Assessment
MyST	Markedly Structured Text
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OSM	Open Street Map
PDF	Portable Document Format
PM	Person Month
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PyPI	Python Package Index

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
REST	Representational State Transfer
SPAM	Spatial Production Allocation Model
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogue
USGS	United States Geological Survey
WMO	World Meteorological Organisation
WP	Work Package
WRI	World Resources Institute
XML	Extensible Markup Language
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language, for human-readable data serialization

Executive summary

This document presents the updated Data Management Plan (DMP) of the CLIMAAX project in M30. It describes the strategy for managing the data collected, (re)used, adapted and created by the project partners, together with recommendations and requirements for beneficiaries of the financial support for third parties. The motivation for data collection and creation is stated in the context of the project objectives. Technical information on data formats and access are summarized and a list of relevant datasets managed for the implementation of the climate risk assessment handbook is provided. This DMP aims to for the CLIMAAX related-data to follow FAIR principles, i.e., ensuring it is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Information is provided on resource allocations for data management in the project and the measures taken to protect sensitive data.

This deliverable is primarily targeted at the consortium partners and should serve as a reference for the management of data products used in the project. It also serves to support the development of new data products in the project. All CLIMAAX partners should refer to this plan to ensure a consistent approach to the sharing and documentation of datasets (including metadata).

The final update of the DMP will be delivered in M44 as deliverable D8.8.

1 Data summary

Data plays a vital part in the CLIMAAX climate risk assessment handbook, particularly as input to the risk workflows that facilitate the quantitative risk analysis step. The handbook supports users of the integrated workflows with information on existing and reusable datasets that can be utilized in their risk analysis. This information is provided via dedicated pages in the handbook and as part of the workflows. The workflow descriptions include information on data requirements and aim to help users to select relevant datasets. All workflows are preconfigured with public datasets and the project provides sample data to further illustrate the usage of a selection of workflows. Automated data collection, where possible, is part of the workflow steps just as data processing and visualization are.

The data collected for a workflow characterizes the elements of hazard, exposure and vulnerability that are combined in the workflows into indicators of risk (CLIMAAX, 2024c). In the context of the CLIMAAX risk assessment framework, the data thus helps users in the assessment of risk and the potential impacts of climate change on society and the environment for an area of interest. The assessment further supports the development of strategies to mitigate and adapt to these risks by regional authorities.

Because the focus of CLIMAAX is on regional climate risk assessment, data of high spatial resolution, from kilometer-scale to the level of individual buildings, are highly desirable. However, this requirement is associated with significant challenges related to data availability, volume and processing.

1.1 Types of data

Data relevant for the risk workflows can be categorized according to their role in the analysis:

- **Hazard data** describe the physical characteristics and potential impacts of natural hazards such as floods, wildfires, droughts, and heatwaves.
- **Climate data** are used to produce hazard data as part of the hazard assessment in the risk workflows when suitable hazard indicators are not directly available. We broadly consider observations and reanalysis data as well as outputs from climate model projections as climate data.
- **Exposure and vulnerability data** describe the elements at risk, such as population, buildings, infrastructure, and ecosystems, as well as their susceptibility to damage or disruption from natural hazards.
- **Risk data** combine hazard, exposure, and vulnerability to estimate the likelihood and potential consequences of natural hazards for a given area of interest. While there are some providers of prepared risk data that can directly be used in a risk assessment, this type of data is primarily generated as output of the risk workflows.

1.2 Data formats

The formats in which data are stored and transferred are mainly selected based on the data's content and shape. Data used in the CLIMAAX workflows extend across a large range of dimensionality, from simple one-dimensional damage curves to complex high-

dimensional climate, hazard and risk datasets that are resolved in time and space and may contain information for multiple climate models, future scenarios and/or risk thresholds. Our choices of data formats aim to ensure adherence to established community practices and broad compatibility with software environments already used by the handbook's target audience (in particular, GIS).

Gridded multidimensional data are the most common inputs and outputs of the risk workflows in the handbook. These datasets usually represent horizontal fields over the globe or a limited geographical area and collections thereof. Examples are fields of temperature or precipitation produced by a climate model, maps of event return periods or population density and land-use classifications. Gridded data are almost always provided in NetCDF, GeoTIFF, Zarr or GRIB formats by external data providers and written as such in the workflows. These standardized formats allow for storing metadata such as information on coordinate reference systems alongside the data and often support encoding and compression of values to reduce size. These formats are understood by the xarray package and associated plugins in Python, the programming language used in the CLIMAAX handbook. They are also widely understood by GIS applications.

Non-gridded geographical data, e.g., definitions of an area of interest or historical fire records, are stored in specialized geolocated vector formats, primarily Shapefiles and GeoJSON. Tabular data, e.g., spatially aggregated datasets of small volume or event databases, are stored in CSV or Office Open XML formats. These formats are handled with the pandas and geopandas Python packages in the workflows. Tabular data are additionally accessible with spreadsheet editors like Microsoft Excel.

Image data in formats such as PNG and JPEG are used to enhance visualisations in the workflows, e.g., in the form of image tiles accessed through web map services. Image formats are also used to store graphical workflow outputs intended for distribution in reports or presentations.

Next to the data processed as part of the workflows, a significant part of the project's output takes the form of text, video and software. Text content in the handbook is written in the Markdown format stored in plain text files and Jupyter Notebooks and is converted to HTML for display on the handbook website. MyST Markdown extensions and custom HTML with associated CSS styling are further used to enhance the visual style of the handbook and risk workflows. Documents such as deliverable reports, scientific publications and presentation slides are published as PDF files.

All software published by the CLIMAAX project is distributed as source code in plain text files to be executed in a Python runtime environment. Specifications of the required environments for all risk workflows are distributed in a YAML format suitable for the conda package manager or a requirements text file for the pip package manager.

1.3 Reused data

We aim to reuse existing data as much as possible in the risk workflows of the CLIMAAX handbook. A vast number of datasets is available online from open repositories and can be used under permissive licenses for the purpose of assessing climate risks. Every risk workflow in the handbook is configured to work with one or multiple public datasets by default, contains information on data access and, where possible, also includes an

implementation for automated data retrieval as part of the Jupyter notebooks. The datasets used by default in the risk workflows of the handbook are primarily selected for their content but also to practically demonstrate how different data formats and sources can be included in a quantitative risk analysis.

An order-of-magnitude estimate for the volume of reused data in a CLIMAAX risk assessment workflow is about 10 gigabyte. Workflows that rely on pre-processed hazard datasets or use providers that allow for convenient selective data retrieval may require an order of magnitude less. Users interested in exploring the full range of uncertainty in future projections of all components of risk may have to retrieve data volumes of an order of magnitude greater.

For detailed information on reused datasets in CLIMAAX, we refer to the dataset inventories that were created for public deliverables D2.2 (CLIMAAX, 2024a) and D2.3 (CLIMAAX, 2024b). Condensed versions of these inventories are also maintained in the online handbook and a STAC (Reimann et al., 2024). Here, we give only a brief overview of reused datasets from the risk workflows and the providers we obtain them from.

1.3.1 Datasets by provider

The following list is based on version 2025.04.1 of the CLIMAAX handbook.

Climatologies at high resolution for the Earth's land surface areas (CHELSA)

A global downscaled climate dataset (Karger et al., 2017), hosted by the Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research at <https://chelsa-climate.org/>. We access data directly from their download server via HTTPS.

Copernicus

The Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) provides access to a variety of climate data and a range of derived climate indicator products. We request and retrieve data from CDS with the cdsapi Python package (ECMWF, 2024).

- ERA5 (C3S, 2023a, 2023b).
- CORDEX (C3S, 2019a).
- Sea level change time series (C3S, 2022b).
- Sea level change indicators (C3S, 2022a).
- Heat waves and cold spells (C3S, 2019b).
- Fire danger indicators (C3S, 2020).
- Winter windstorm indicators (C3S, 2022c).

The Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) provides geographical information on land cover, land use, ground motions, vegetation state, water cycle and Earth's surface energy variables. We access data via the online CLMS catalogue at <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/dataset-catalog>.

- CORINE land cover (European Environment Agency, 2019)

The Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) provides information for emergency response and disaster risk management.

- We access various datasets via the EFFIS Wildfire Risk Viewer (EFFIS, 2025).
- Historical burnt area polygons can be requested through an online form at <https://forest-fire.emergency.copernicus.eu/apps/data.request.form/>.
- Global Human Settlement Layer, available in the online download portal (JRC, 2024).

Eurostat

Statistics and data on Europe from the statistical office of the European Union (Eurostat). We access data from the Geographic Information System of the Commission (GISCO) via a REST API at <https://gisco-services.ec.europa.eu/distribution/v2/>.

- Boundaries of NUTS regions (GISCO, 2024).

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)

Datasets available for download from the Food Insecurity, Poverty and Environment Global GIS Database (FGGD) at <https://data.apps.fao.org/catalog/dataset>.

- Thermal climate zones of the world (FAO, 2007).

Datasets available for download via the Global Agro-Ecological Zones (GAEZ) v4 data portal (FAO and IIASA, 2021) at <https://gaez.fao.org/>.

- Actual Yield and Production: Aggregate Crop Production Value.
- Land and Water Resources: Cropland, equipped for full control irrigation.

Harvard Dataverse

A free data repository open to all researchers to share, archive, cite, access, and explore research data. We access data with the pyDataverse Python package (Kasberger et al., 2024).

- Crop production statistics for 2010 based on the Spatial Production Allocation Model (SPAM) of the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI, 2019).

ISIMIP Repository

Climate and climate-related forcing data for simulations of the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP), available for download from <https://data.isimip.org/>.

- ISIMIP3a (Lange et al., 2023): historical data.
- ISIMIP3b (Lange & Büchner, 2021): bias-corrected CMIP6 projections.

Joint Research Centre (JRC)

The JRC Data Catalogue is an inventory of data produced by the JRC. We retrieve datasets from the open data portal at <https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ftp/jrc-opendata/> and the JRC publications repository.

- River flood hazard maps (Baugh et al., 2024).
- LUISA land cover (Pigaiani & Batista e Silva, 2021).
- Flood depth-damage functions (Huizinga et al., 2017).

Microsoft Planetary Computer

A cloud-based catalogue of global environmental data. We access data through the Planetary Computer STAC API with the planetary-computer (Microsoft, 2023) and pystac-client (stac-utils, 2025) Python packages.

- Deltares Global Flood Maps (Deltares, 2021).

OpenStreetMap

Community-driven and open map data available from <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>. We access building types and footprints with the osmnx Python package (Boeing, 2025).

RSLab Products

Land surface temperature derived from Landsat satellite images (Parastatidis et al., 2017). Data downloads must be configured with a web application maintained by the Remote Sensing Lab of the Foundation for research and technology – Hellas at https://www.rslab.gr/Landsat_LST.html.

USGS EROS Center

Datasets from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS) Center are available for download through the EarthExplorer web application at <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>.

- Landsat collection 2 level 1 products (EROS, 2020). We access data through the USGS/EROS Machine-to-Machine API with the usgs (Kapadia, 2025) and eodag (CS GROUP, 2025) Python packages.
- Digital elevation model (EROS, 2017).

WorldPop Hub

Open spatial demographic datasets, available for download from <https://hub.worldpop.org/>.

- Gridded population estimates of total number of people per cell broken down by gender and age groupings (WorldPop, 2018).

Zenodo

Open access repository for research outputs, such as publications, datasets, software, and posters. We access data from Zenodo records via the pooch Python package (Uieda et al., 2020).

- ECLIPS-2.0: gridded climate data for Europe (Chakraborty et al., 2020).
- Soil Available Water Capacity (Hengl & Gupta, 2019).
- Fire Weather Index Simulations over Europe (El Garroussi, 2024).
- IPCC AR6 Sea Level Projections (Garner et al., 2021).

World Resources Institute (WRI)

A global research organization with a broad open access catalogue of data, available at <https://www.wri.org/data>.

- Aqueduct floods hazard maps (Aqueduct, 2020).

1.3.2 Rehosted datasets

Some datasets, though available from a public repository, are only accessible in an inconvenient way for the purposes of the CLIMAAX risk workflows. A selection of such datasets has been transformed into more conveniently accessible data structures and is rehosted in a cloud storage instance maintained by ECMWF for CLIMAAX. Each rehosted dataset has an accompanying page in the CLIMAAX handbook with information on its origin and the applied transformations. These dataset “mirrors” will be maintained at minimum for the duration of the project.

Rehosted datasets in version 2025.04.1 of the CLIMAAX handbook:

- **ECLIPS-2.0** (Chakraborty et al., 2020), partially rehosted (only a selection of variables provided) with access to individual files instead of packaging all data into a single compressed archive as in the original data source. No data transformation applied.
- **EFFIS Wildfire Risk** (EFFIS, 2025), direct access to GeoTIFF files without the requirement to extract information from compressed archives as in the original source. No data transformation applied.
- **FWI simulations with CMIP6-informed perturbations** (El Garroussi, 2024), rehosted as a chunked Zarr dataset (original data provided in GRIB-format). Dataset dimensions are transposed for improved local-in-space access and values are reencoded as 16-bit integers with a scale factor and offset to reduce the size of the dataset.

1.3.3 Inclusion of local data by workflow users

Users of the CLIMAAX handbook are strongly encouraged to find additional sources of relevant information that can be used for their climate risk assessment. Local data that are of higher resolution, more recent and/or produced from models tailored to the local conditions may be available as better alternatives to the global or European-scale datasets listed above. Workflows provide entry points for such datasets, and the project’s financial support for third parties (FSTP) beneficiaries receive advice and software support for the inclusion of additional datasets. However, it is the primary responsibility of the users to identify additional data for their area of interest based on their local expertise and the guidance provided by the handbook.

1.4 Created data

1.4.1 Ready-to-go datasets for workflows

Some risk workflows in the handbook require users to retrieve and process large amounts of data even for basic applications. To allow users to get to know these workflows without committing to such efforts, CLIMAAX project partners can provide pre-processed datasets. They may also provide example data to illustrate how workflows expect local input data to be structured. These datasets are made available on the CLIMAAX cloud storage and have a corresponding page in the CLIMAAX handbook with information on their contents and use. We expect these datasets to change in response to user feedback over the duration of the project. Once a dataset has been reviewed and tested by users, it will be archived in a citable record within the CLIMAAX community on Zenodo.

Ready-to-go datasets in version 2025.04.1 of the CLIMAAX handbook:

- **Drought risk data:** precomputed monthly precipitation data and hazard, exposure and vulnerability indicators at NUTS3 level over geographical Europe. Created as a sample dataset for the relative drought workflow.
- **Precipitation pre-calculated IDF:** intensity, duration and frequency of precipitation events computed for multiple EURO-CORDEX models. Example input data for the extreme precipitation workflow is additionally included for Catalonia, Spain. Created to provide users of the extreme precipitation workflow with a ready-to-go hazard dataset.
- **Wildfire training and vulnerability data:** collection of hazard, exposure and vulnerability data for the region of Catalonia, Spain, as an example of the input data required for the wildfire (machine-learning approach) workflow.

1.4.2 The handbook

The open-access CLIMAAX handbook is available as a website at <https://handbook.climaax.eu/> and its source code is hosted in code repositories on GitHub where project partners collaborate on the development. Modifications to all handbook content and software are managed and recorded with the git version control system.

1.4.3 User surveys and interviews

Work package 7 of CLIMAAX collects data from the project's pilot region partners and FSTP beneficiaries as part of a monitoring system for the usability, relevance and impact of the CLIMAAX framework and workflows. This data are collected through surveys, interviews and focus groups.

1.4.4 Reports, publications and videos

All public deliverables are available from the CLIMAAX website¹. Links to preprints, journal articles and conference contributions are collected on a dedicated page of the website². Video media are uploaded to the YouTube channel of project partner CMCC³ where they can be viewed on demand. Links to uploaded webinar recordings and the corresponding slide decks are collected on an archive page of the website⁴ and recordings from meetings of the Community of Practice (CoP) are collected on a dedicated CoP page⁵. Video guides for handbook content are embedded directly in the handbook website.

1.4.5 Supporting Information for Deliverables from FSTP Beneficiaries

Beneficiaries of the project's FSTP are required to provide supporting material with their deliverable documents. With this material, beneficiaries can illustrate in more detail how they have applied the CLIMAAX framework and workflows and provide output data to the project partners. This information is used to improve the handbook throughout the project

¹ <https://www.climaax.eu/public-deliverables/>

² <https://www.climaax.eu/journal-papers/>

³ <https://www.youtube.com/@CMCCvideo>

⁴ <https://www.climaax.eu/archive/>

⁵ <https://www.climaax.eu/community-of-practice/>

and, if suitable, outputs will be synthesized into a European-scale dataset at the end of the project.

2 FAIR principles for data

Enabling users to find, access and reuse existing datasets to conduct a quantitative analysis that supports their climate risk assessment is an important objective of the CLIMAAX handbook. The FAIR principles,

- *Findable* (through standards for identification and metadata),
- *Accessible* (how data are accessed during and after the project lifetime),
- *Interoperable* (defining a sharing policy and integration into workflows) and
- *Reusable* (including clear licensing and correct formatting of data and metadata)

are therefore central to the data management of the project. Since most datasets utilized in the project are reused, attention is paid to select FAIR-compliant data providers as much as possible. CLIMAAX follows an open-by-default development model guided by the FAIR principles for the handbook and associated data. Unless special restrictions apply, project outputs are openly available through the handbook and project websites and created with interoperability and reusability in mind.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Enhancing findability of reusable data with the handbook

The CLIMAAX handbook is a resource that supports users in finding and discovering datasets that they can use for the assessment of climate-related risks. Information on reusable datasets have been collected on dedicated data inventory pages in the Handbook and in a STAC (Reimann et al., 2024). All risk workflows are equipped with dataset recommendations by default. For these recommendations, we prefer providers with searchable catalogues, such as the CDS, whose catalogue can be accessed through a STAC-compliant API⁶.

As part of the CLIMAAX CRA framework, users are encouraged to seek out the best local data for their area of interest to use in a workflow application. We intend to take up the experience gained by the FSTP beneficiaries in collecting such data to improve the handbook's data inventory and guidance throughout the project.

Within the workflows, we adapt to the naming and metadata conventions of the data providers. We give preference to providers that adhere to standardized naming and metadata conventions (e.g., CF, OGC) and who document custom standards where used. Making the workflows compatible with these standards encourages users to follow the same standards for their local data during integration.

2.1.2 Findability of handbook content, rehosted and created datasets

The CLIMAAX handbook is a public website indexed by major search engine providers and all pages can additionally be searched with a built-in search function on the website.

⁶ See <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/stac-browser/>.

All changes to handbook content and the software distributed by CLIMAAX are recorded with the git version control system and published under the umbrella of a CLIMAAX organization on GitHub. Frozen-in-time snapshots of the handbook and workflow repository contents are taken in non-regular intervals and tagged with version numbers following a calendar versioning scheme. These snapshots serve as releases of the handbook and release notes are published alongside on GitHub⁷ to inform users and developers of important changes to the handbook and associated components. All GitHub releases will be synchronized to a citable and persistent record of the handbook on Zenodo in the future.

Rehosted datasets and datasets created by project partners are findable through dedicated dataset pages in the handbook and their integration into the risk workflows. These dedicated pages provide metadata and technical information about the corresponding datasets. When created datasets are moved from the CLIMAAX cloud storage to Zenodo at the end of the project, they additionally become findable through Zenodo's API and receive a citable DOI.

Supporting material submitted by the FSTP beneficiaries to the CLIMAAX Zenodo community is findable through the Zenodo API. Notably, the metadata of these records is findable even if beneficiaries restrict access to the contents. We are evaluating possibilities to synthesize these submitted records into a European-scale dataset, to be deposited in an existing portal for risk data, e.g., the JRC risk data hub.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Open-access handbook and publications

The CLIMAAX handbook and all related software is developed under an open-source model. The source code for all handbook content is hosted in public repositories on GitHub, where project partners work cooperatively in a transparent development process. The GitHub platform also makes the handbook accessible to the wider community. It allows external developers and users to contribute to the development by raising issues and pull requests. A contribution guide and code of conduct are included with the handbook to facilitate such external contributions.

All project-related publications in scientific journals are made open-access immediately after publication. Associated data are deposited in open-access repositories such as Zenodo and Figshare.

2.2.2 Data access and documentation

The executable risk workflows are the primary format in which data access instructions are provided to handbook users. In the workflows, concrete and practical examples are given of how to access data from the providers listed in sections 1.3 and 1.4.1 with software from the Python ecosystem. These providers are selected for their open access policies. Some require users to create a free account to authenticate with their API and retrieve data from their catalogue.

Where datasets are inconvenient to access from a provider, CLIMAAX partners can choose to rehost these datasets on the CLIMAAX cloud storage in a more accessible way for the

⁷ <https://github.com/CLIMAAX/crabook/releases>

project lifetime (c.f. section 1.3.2). Data deposited in this cloud storage are openly accessible for reading via the HTTPS protocol. For all file-centric datasets on the cloud storage (rehosted or created), an associated plain-text file registry document is provided on a corresponding handbook dataset page. This registry can be loaded by the pooch Python package (Uieda et al., 2020) to access files programmatically and verify their integrity after download. The required steps are documented in the handbook. Accessibility beyond the project lifetime will be ensured by archiving all created datasets as public records on Zenodo.

The handbook guides users through the process of setting up the software environments required to access datasets as illustrated in the workflows. The Python runtime and all software packages included in these curated software environments are available free of charge from open repositories (conda-forge, PyPI or directly from GitHub). Package specifications and installation instructions are maintained in the relevant repositories in the CLIMAAX GitHub organization. The FSTP beneficiaries of the project can request access to a JupyterHub web interface to ECMWF-hosted cloud computing infrastructure for the duration of their projects, where a full-featured software environment is maintained.

2.2.3 Access-restricted data

Sensitive data collected by WP7 from the CLIMAAX pilot project partners and FSTP beneficiaries are equipped with access restrictions. Non-anonymized data from surveys and interview recordings are only accessible by the project members who evaluate the responses and will be deleted at the end of the project.

FSTP beneficiaries may include sensitive local data in their risk assessments which they need to protect with access restrictions to comply with restrictions on content sharing and their individual legal requirements. User data uploaded to the CLIMAAX JupyterHub are access controlled through the users' accounts with ECMWF. Users are advised to follow the handbook instructions for setting up a local software environment if they need to retain full control over their data. Beneficiaries retain access control over their submitted Zenodo records (section 1.4.5) but are required to grant access to project partners for evaluation purposes. This access is implemented through inclusion of the records in the CLIMAAX community on Zenodo which project members can only join by invitation.

2.3 Making data interoperable

CLIMAAX aims to make the data created and reused in the project interoperable within and across disciplines. The data formats encountered in the project, listed in section 1.2, are established formats in their user communities with strong software support and documentation. The risk workflows in the handbook provide concrete instructions for operating with this data. They show by example how data from different providers and disciplines can be combined for the purpose of risk assessment, e.g., by matching and translating metadata vocabularies. Users are encouraged to plug-in their own datasets into the workflows, either by adapting the workflows to accommodate the supplied data formats and conventions or by transforming the data to match the requirements of the default datasets as used and documented in the workflows.

The experience of the pilot partners and FSTP beneficiaries as they work with input and output data of the workflows and integrate them into their existing data handling practices

allows CLIMAAX partners to assess the state of data interoperability and develop the handbook to address identified shortcomings.

2.4 Increase data reuse

Data reuse is a central principle in the CLIMAAX handbook. As part of the CLIMAAX Framework and workflows, users are guided to reuse existing datasets in their climate risk assessment. The risk workflows from the Handbook are implemented such that outputs are reusable within the users' organisations and can be shared with relevant stakeholders. Through the practice of the FSTP beneficiaries, project partners receive immediate feedback on the reusability of data. The experience gained is used to improve reusability aspects in the handbook throughout the project lifetime.

Datasets with permissive licenses are preferentially used as defaults in the risk workflows. Data created by CLIMAAX partners are distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY) license unless restriction apply that prevent this choice. The software in all public CLIMAAX repositories is licensed under the Apache License 2.0 and the handbook is dual licensed under both CC-BY and the Apache License 2.0.

The open development model of the handbook means all related content and data are made available as soon as a sufficient level of quality has been established by relevant experts from the project partners in an internal review process. Additional external reviews are conducted as part of the submission process for public deliverables and scientific publications. Automated software quality assurance checks are implemented for all workflow repositories on GitHub. Data-related issues flagged by users of the handbook are either addressed by project partners directly (created datasets) or documented in the workflows, with solutions implemented in the code where possible (reused datasets).

The CLIMAAX project strives to create a legacy of open resources that can be reused by the climate risk assessment community beyond the lifetime of the project. Long-term archival of the handbook and created datasets in repositories like Zenodo will ensure that these resources remain accessible and reusable. However, data providers may remove datasets from their catalogues or change the APIs with which to access them. Risk workflows may cease to function after backwards-incompatible updates to software packages, while the original package versions from the provided CLIMAAX Python environments may pose security risks in the future. Such events inevitably limit the long-term reusability of *some* project outputs. However, the open-source approach taken by the project will allow the user community to continue maintaining and building on its resources.

3 Allocation of resources

The costs required for making relevant data FAIR have been included in the budget of the project. Deltares as project coordinator have the overall responsibility for the delivery of the project, ECMWF and the Task 8.2 team have the primary responsibility for creating, updating and delivering the data management plan. Specifically, ECMWF has dedicated 9 PM to WP8, and most of this will be dedicated to the implementation and updating of the DMP. All project partners are involved in the support of the overall data management plan or by ensuring their contributions adhere to the principles established therein. WP2 has provided

details on the data used in the Handbook in Deliverables D2.2 (CLIMAAX, 2024a) and D2.3 (CLIMAAX, 2024b). The related costs have been included in the contribution of each partner.

Reused datasets for the risk workflows are accessed directly from the individual providers and only free-to-access datasets are chosen as defaults for the workflows of the Handbook. Rehosted datasets (1.3.2) and datasets created by CLIMAAX partners (section 1.4.1) are stored on ECMWF's Common Cloud Infrastructure (CCI) and will be archived on Zenodo at the end of the project. FSTP beneficiaries submit data as part of their deliverables to Zenodo (section 1.4.5) and retain control of their submissions on the platform. It is envisioned that a curated selection of this submitted data will be preserved in the JRC Risk data hub.

Storage for user data of the CLIMAAX JupyterHub is provided on ECMWF's CCI for the duration of the project.

4 Data security

Reused datasets (section 1.3.1) are stored by the respective data providers and only copies are retrieved by users from project partners and FSTP beneficiaries. Rehosted (section 1.3.2) and created (section 1.4.1) datasets are stored on ECMWF cloud storage with copies maintained locally by the respective contributing partners. The processing steps taken by project partners to produce datasets are documented and the workflow notebooks document the steps required to reproduce risk assessment results. All data published on Zenodo are subject to Zenodo's backup and recovery policy⁸.

⁸ <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

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